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Evaluating edge-enabled smart waste management in smart cities: A design-oriented KVI/KPI framework.

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Abstract. Rapid urbanisation has intensified the pressure on municipal waste management, exposing the limits of conventional, capacity-driven service models. Edge-computing now enables smart-waste solutions that improve operational efficiency by processing data closer to the point of collection. Yet, as concern grows over the societal impact of technology-enabled urban systems, edge-enabled smart city systems are increasingly expected to demonstrate not only technical efficiency but also sustainability, social, and business value. Evaluation practice, however, remains siloed: low-level system performance is typically assessed separately from the broader public-value outcomes at stake, leaving decision-makers without a coherent basis for judging whether a deployment delivers value beyond the technical layers. This paper addresses that gap by proposing a three-dimensional KPI-KVI framework for evaluating edge-enabled smart waste management systems, in which measurable Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) are explicitly linked to the higher-order Key Value Indicators (KVI). The framework is derived from a focused review of evaluation literature, stakeholder input, and a live edge-IoT pilot in Valencia, Spain, conducted within the COP-PILOT Horizon Europe project. Twenty KVIs, operationalised through twenty-two KPIs, are organised across sustainability, social, and business-value dimensions and mapped to corresponding value outcomes. Pilot measurements indicate an approximately 53% reduction in memory usage through split services and a 6.9-second actuation time from sensor activation to service deployment, providing evidence at the system layer for the framework's efficiency and sustainability dimensions. We do not claim end-to-end validation of public-value outcomes; rather, these results indicate that a split-service edge architecture offers a plausible pathway toward operational efficiency, sustainability, and public value, with wider outcomes to be confirmed through longitudinal KPI-to-KVI assessment.

Keywords. Smart waste management, Edge computing, Public value evaluation, KPI-KVI framework, Smart cities, Sustainability.

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1. Introduction

Increased in urban challenges today escalates complexity in waste management. The city's solid waste globally is estimated to achieve 3.4 billion tonnes per year by 2050 (World Bank, 2018). This potentially increases logistical issues in waste collection. As waste collection logistics in many cities is determined by rigid schedules, the level of

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fill of the waste containers is not taken into consideration, causing unnecessary vehicle movements, excessive fuel consumption and greenhouse gas emissions. Meanwhile, the overflowed waste containers lead to health-related sanitation issues and decreased quality of living in urban areas.

Smart cities research has suggested using sensor systems, data analysis, and optimised routes for waste collection vehicles to improve efficiency in the collection process (Khan et al. 2024). However, the large-scale deployments of cloud-based architectures for these solutions generate new critical issues, namely network latency degrades timely decision-making, continuous data transfer from sensors increases energy usage and raise privacy concerns, and reliance on centralised cloud-based systems reduce the ability to maintain resiliency. Edge computing, which moves computational logic closer to the physical infrastructure, offers a structural solution to these problems (Shi, 2016). However, deploying edge computing in real-world urban settings is technically complex and lacks governing institutions.

COP-PILOT (Collaborative Open Platform for Piloting Services Across Emerging Smart IoT and Edge Computing Environments, Horizon Europe Grant No. 101189819) is addressing this challenge on a large scale. Consisting of 46 partners in 12 European countries, COP-PILOT developed an open, standards-based platform that integrates ETSI NGSI-LD semantic data modelling, ETSI MEC-aligned orchestration via OpenSlice, and zero-trust secure connectivity through OpenZiti. Valencia, designated as European Green Capital 2024, serves as the main urban piloting environment, with use cases located on the UPV Campus and the Port of Valencia (the fifth largest port in Europe). In this context, the smart waste management use case at UPV (UC2.2) utilises Narrowband-IoT (NB-IoT) sensors to measure the fill levels of waste containers on the campus. These sensors trigger edge local analytics only when the container reaches the threshold that demands action, optimising the collection route. This demand-driven split service approach creates a unique dataset of idle resource consumption to actuation delay that has never before been tied to an evaluation framework designed to assess the benefits created across the entire sustainably-society-business spectrum.

This paper has three-fold contributions. Firstly, it provides a structured framework to evaluate edge-computing-based IT infrastructure across three dimensions: sustainability, societal impact and business value, each comprising key value indicators and performance indicators that are grounded in theory, validated for face validity by domain experts, and partially calibrated against pilot data. Full empirical validation of the social, sustainability and business-value outcomes remains the subject of subsequent pilot phases. Secondly, it demonstrates how specific design decisions in smart city applications (split-service implementation, semantic interoperability, zero-trust networking) directly influence indicator values and thus provide practitioners with a basis for design rationale rather than simply measuring the effects after the fact. Finally, it contextualises the proposed evaluation framework within the broader body of literature on evaluating smart cities, highlighting its different stance from previous approaches that emphasise either narrow, operational measures or broad, governance-oriented measures, and typically do not link both levels together.

The remainder of the paper is organised as follows. Section 2 reviews relevant literature. Section 3 describes the UPV pilot architecture and the experimental outcomes. Section 4 details the methodology used to develop the mixed methods framework. Section 5 fully elaborates the KPI/KVI framework. Section 6 identifies the theoretical and practical implications of the findings. Section 7 provides conclusions and specifies avenues for future research.

2. Literature review

2.1 Smart cities, sustainability imperative and public value

Early Smart-City discussions primarily saw "Smart" as an efficient use of technology to increase the ability of Urban Service Delivery through ICTs. The three key policy objectives were data integration, automation and real-time control (Akande et al., 2019; Prasad et al., 2022). Subsequent research then challenged this technocentric approach to being too focused on efficiency, and ignoring issues related to environmental justice, social inclusion, and long-term resilience. Instead, there was an emergence of the concept of "Smart and Sustainable Cities," where environmental performance, social well-being and economic viability would become the main objective instead of layering the top of technological modernisation (Akande et al., 2019; Fang et al., 2023).

Public Value Theory expands upon this critique by stating that digital government and smart city initiatives should be evaluated based on shared community values, like sustainability, equity, transparency, and quality of life (Prasad et al., 2022; Akande et al., 2019), as opposed to solely measuring them on their own internal efficiency and technical capabilities (Fang et al., 2023; Akande et al., 2019). This re-framing puts forward the normative question of "value for whom, and under what conditions?" and makes smart city projects socio-technical interventions that can create value with various publics in multiple areas of environmental, social and economic spaces (Fang et al., 2023; Akande et al., 2019).

In response to the above, standards and indicator systems like ISO 37120/37122, ITU-T Y.4903 and CITYkeys, attempted to operationalise multi-dimensional conceptions of smart city performance through hierarchical sets of indicators that align with SDGs (Akande et al., 2019; Prasad et al., 2022). However, critical evaluations of these systems have shown that they are often just re-package existing managerial logic, promoting the idea of aggregating city-wide rankings, and creating a conceptual gap between sensor-layer measurement and governance-relevant results at the service level (ITU-T, 2020; Fang et al., 2023). The most common sustainability-related aspects in smart city initiatives include resource efficiency, emissions reduction, circular economy practices, and climate risk resilience (Akande et al., 2019; COP-PILOT Consortium, 2025a). Focus regarding who receives benefits, and who incurs costs, are usually undermined (Akande et al., 2019).

Waste Management is often seen as a crucial leverage point for achieving sustain-able urban development due to the close association it has with consumption patterns, logistics and local environmental quality. Nonetheless, many municipalities still do not have service-level data to measure and optimise their waste collection services, preventing them from making strong public-value claims for those services (Wall and Martin, 2003; Startup Financial Projection, 2025).

Edge-enabled smart-waste systems is seen as potential solution to bridge the current data gap by linking detailed operational data to larger sustainability and public-value objectives. Yet, the potential for edge-enabled Smart-Waste Systems remains largely untapped with the absent of an evaluation framework that measures beyond the narrowly defined technical key performance indicators (KPIs) in evaluating the broader socio-economic and governance implications (Fang et al., 2023).

2.2 Smart cities, stakeholders and impact evaluation

The increasing focus on the relational aspects of smart cities has created a new line of inquiry in smart city research. The value creation process in smart city scholarship will no longer be dependent on the use of smart technologies but rather on how these technologies are configured within the relationships between various stakeholders. The application of Stakeholder Theory (Freeman, 1984) illustrates that smart city projects include multiple stakeholders with diverse levels of interest, resource and power, e.g. municipal authorities, campus managers, technology providers, operators, citizens and local businesses. Stakeholder Theory argues the heterogeneity of stakeholders creates an environment where each group frames problems differently, de-signs solutions based on their own needs and interprets the perceived impacts of the solution (Prasad et al., 2022; Akande et al., 2019).

Studies suggest that superficial consultations amongst stakeholders reinforce pre-existing hierarchies of power, while collaborative approaches may highlight disparate views regarding issues of data governance, risk sharing and the distribution of benefits (Fang et al., 2023). In the context of services such as smart waste management, the service evaluation must be approached from multitude level of analysis. For instance, evaluating the service at a system-level as well as addressing the concerns of campus operations and city services, the viability of business models for technology vendors, local businesses impacted by logistics and end-users experiencing altered service delivery, data collection and environmental implications (Startup Financial Projections, 2025).

Inadvertently, the treatment of Key Performance Indicators (KPI) as neutral descriptions of service delivery performance is increasingly being problematised, as indicators are treated as value-laden tools serving to promote specific interests and framing options of stakeholders. This includes examples such as prioritising cost savings and optimisation over equity and long-term capability development (Akande et al., 2019; Fang et al., 2023). Therefore, integrating public value and stakeholder-oriented perspectives requires the development of impact assessment frameworks that identify and explicitly link technical measures of performance to social, economic and governance-based outcomes and highlight the interests of stakeholders that are promoted through the adoption of such systems and those that are marginalised and how trade-offs related to efficiency, sustainability and inclusion are negotiated over time (Prasad et al., 2022). As a result of this, the case for applying a socio-economic, business and sustainability lens to the evaluation of edge-technology-led projects is strengthened (Khan et al., 2020). Such a lens will enable evaluators to consider both operational performance and the broader public-value dimensions associated with deploying and scaling such systems.

2.3 Smart Waste Management

The smart-waste literature has documented a succession of waves of innovation, from early days using RFID-tagged containers and GPS-monitored vehicles through to today's deployments using container level-sensors, low-power communication networks (NB-IoT, LoRaWAN) and route-optimisation engines integrated into cloud-based platforms (Startup Financial Projection, 2025; Haque et al., 2020). Empirical evidence often identifies the reductions in collection frequency, fuel consumption and overflow incidents resulting from smart waste systems, but the literature rarely addresses the institutional arrangements, behavioural changes and socioeconomic factors influencing the effectiveness of these smart systems (Startup Financial Projection, 2025; Wall and Martin, 2003).

Operational KPI sets in smart waste management typically include metrics such as miles travelled, fuel consumption, tonnes collected per trip, coverage, complaint rates. Although these metrics are essential for evaluating service delivery efficiency, they do little to address issues related to equity, stakeholder satisfaction or innovation capability. Smart city evaluation research argues that an operational focus is limited in terms of representing sustainability and public value dimensions and therefore recommend the development of frameworks that incorporate a broader set of indicators, including those measuring emissions reduction, citizen experience and organisational learning (Fang et al., 2023; Akande et al., 2019).

Edge-enabled smart-waste projects, due to the granularity of the data generated and the flexibility in the orchestration of those systems, provide the best opportunity for developing and implementing such broadened evaluations. Conversely, relatively few studies have proposed transferable indicator sets for policymakers to utilise in assessing edge-enabled smart-waste systems across different settings.

2.4 Edge computing, distributed architectures and evaluation frameworks

Latency, bandwidth and reliability are the key aspects underpinning the efficiency of edge computing architecture. Latency and backhaul congestion will be reduced when the computing is brought closer to the data source, making data processing more energy efficient (Aazam and Huh, 2016). Furthermore, extensive surveys of edge-computing-enabled smart cities highlight that while these technical gains are well-documented, a persistent lack of standardized evaluation frameworks remains a hurdle for linking architectural properties to broader urban governance (Khan et al., 2020). In smart cities, hybrid cloud-edge-IOT architectures and standards (i.e. ETSI MEC, NGSI-LD) provide the basis for interoperable, vendor-neutral and context-aware services across domains like mobility, environment and waste (Crespo-Aguado et al., 2026). However, evidence shows that many deployments are still vertically siloed, with very little cross-domain orchestration and a high risk of vendor lock-in, undermining the goals of openness and flexibility (Prasad et al., 2022). The difference between the architecture aspirations and institutional realities of edge computing has significant implications for evaluation. The conventional smart city performance frameworks which are designed primarily at the city scale are poorly equipped to track how specific edge computing properties influence service level outcomes, interoperability, or long-term innovation trajectories (Fang et al., 2023).

Smart city performance systems, such as CITYKeys and other indicator frameworks, use hierarchical KPIs and composite indices to track environmental, social, economic and governance dimensions, and have been useful for benchmarking and strategic monitoring (Houvila et al., 2017, Prasad et al., 2022). Assessment methodologies that focus on ICT (e.g. GeSI and ITU-T), provide detailed tools for quantifying carbon reduction potential and life-cycle environmental impacts of digital technologies. While typically focusing on energy and emissions, they under-represent socio-economic distributional effects and organisational capabilities needed to support edge deployments (Wikström et al., 2024). More recent value-oriented frameworks introduce key value indicators alongside KPIs, particularly in next generation network and 6G research, acknowledging that research and innovation projects generate long-term and intangible value not captured by short-term performance metrics alone (SNS-JU, 2025). From a Theory-of-Change perspective, these developments can be viewed as partial attempts to articulate the causal pathways linking edge technology-based interventions to their intended societal impacts, yet they rarely specify how activities, outputs, intermediate outcomes, such as dynamic orchestration capabilities or new data flows, culminate in concrete changes in sustainability, equity, or economic opportunity (Rogers et al., 2023; Southby et al., 2024).

Therefore, for edge computing enabled smart-waste services, evaluation frameworks must extend beyond operational KPIs to track how architectural properties enable or restrict public value creation over time across environmental, socio-economic and business dimensions (Fang et al., 2023). A socio-economic lens reveals distributional effects and capability changes, e.g. which groups gain improved services, data access or economic opportunities while business lens addresses investment efficiency, market readiness and replicability needed for scaling beyond pilots (Rogers et al. 2023; Kourtzanidis, K. et al., 2021). Bringing these perspectives together within a sustainability-oriented framework provides the groundwork for a more holistic assessment of edge technology led projects, aligns with Public Value Theory, Stakeholder Theory and Theory-of-Change principles, and provides the conceptual basis for the three pillar KPI/KVI structure introduced later in this paper, conceptualised in Figure 1.

Figure 1 - A conceptual diagram showing the relationship between KVs, KVIs and KPIs within the three dimensions (sustainability, societal, business value).

3. Case study: Edge-enabled smart waste management at Universitat Politècnica de València

3.1 Context and objectives

The Universitat Politècnica de València (UPV) is situated on a 450 hectare campus in Valencia, Spain. Committed to achieving carbon neutrality by 2030, and in addition to being part of COP-PILOT's Cluster 2 (Smart City) 'living laboratory' for deploying edge IoT, UPV is more than just a convenient testbed to deploy an IoT solution. It is a realistic yet controlled smart city environment for use case integration and validation. The campus is a self-contained urban district, home to a diverse and dense population of students, academic staff and support personnel who produce the same range of heterogeneous waste streams, e.g. organic, paper, plastic, as those found in mixed-use urban neighbourhoods. With numerous buildings of different types, public open spaces, service roads and logistics access points that are all subject to a unified institutional governance framework, the campus' physical infrastructure resembles that of a medium-density city quarter. In addition, the campus also replicates the operational complexities found in cities due to the fully deployed private 5G advanced network operating over the n40, n258 and n78 frequency bands (in both standalone and non-standalone modes), multiple 5G core configurations, edge cloud continuum infrastructure provided by the iTEAM-UPV institute and integration with Telefónica's FIWARE-based Thinking City platform, which is also used at a city-wide level in Valencia's 825,000-resident metropolitan area. Therefore, since the technical capabilities at the campus level are the same as those in the city level, the findings obtained at the campus level can be directly applied to the city level without needing to alter the architecture, thereby meeting the scalability concerns explicitly highlighted in the blueprint's key pain points. Use Case 2.2 COP-PILOT (UC2.2) addresses the campus waste management lifecycle - from sensor triggered fill-level monitoring to dynamic route optimisation, with the goal of demonstrating that demand-driven, edge-localised intelligence will reduce both operational costs and environmental footprint compared to the traditional fixed schedule approach. The pilot is planned for three phases throughout 2026-2027. Phase 1 includes the deployment of single domain NB-IoT sensors and measure the baseline, phase 2 introduces the split service orchestration model with automated actuation, and phase 3 will extend to multi-domain federation with replication at the Port of Valencia and Almussafes sites to enable cross-domain comparisons and policy transfer experiments.

3.2 Architecture and technical workflow

The system architecture realises the flexible, multi-domain edge model described in Crespo-Aguado et al. (2026). Its main components and their role in the waste management workflow are described below.

The Local Domain at UPV is based on an OpenSlice-based Infrastructure Orchestrator which manages a Kubernetes cluster using Helm charts and Custom Resource Definitions (CRDs). An ETSI NGSI-LD compliant Orion Context

Broker acts as the semantic data layer, normalising the heterogeneous sensor payloads (fill-level per-centage, GPS coordinate, battery state etc.) into a common ontological model. The Secure Integration Fabric (SIF) employs OpenZiti to create secure, zero trust overlay connections between the campus edge nodes and the Central E2E Orchestrator to prevent unauthorised data exposure at intermediate locations. An SLA preservation closed loop (monitoring → decision support → secure actuation) governs the whole workflow: the sensors send out fill-level notifications; when threshold conditions are reached, the decision support module determines the alternative routes; the actuation layer instantiates the route-optimisation microservice on demand and then closes or decommissions it after execution.

An important architectural aspect of the overall system design is the split-service deployment pattern. The route-optimisation service is not always running in memory but only gets instantiated as a container image by the orchestrator when the trigger event occurs. This is the reason why the savings in resources achieved during the pilot study were caused by the fact that the route optimisation service runs only temporarily. Figure 2 illustrates a general overview of the proposed HLA, showing the hierarchical composition of the central domain (cloud level) and the local domains (edge level) via a secure integration fabric and illustrating the end-to-end orchestration and control flow from the Central E2E Orchestrator down to the autonomous Management and Infrastructure layers at the Edge of each Local Domain. For clarity, Figure 3, illustrates the local domain architecture as well as the closed-loop infrastructure management executed by the local domain orchestrator in monitoring, decision support, and secure actuation. In addition to illustrating how the system achieves cross-domain interoperability. Meanwhile, Figure 4 depicts the data ingestion and semantic harmonisation layer, which takes the raw data from disparate, heterogeneous devices, normalises it and maps it to the unified NGSI-LD standard.

Figure 2 - High-Level Architecture (HLA) depicting the end-to-end orchestration and control flow from the Central E2E Orchestrator down to the autonomous Management and Infrastructure layers at the Edge of every Local Domain - adapted from Crespo-Aguado et.al (2026), licensed under CC BY 4.0

Figure 3 - Local Domain architecture details - adapted

from Crespo-Aguado et.al (2026), licensed under CC BY 4.0

Figure 4 - Data Ingestion and Semantic Harmonisation Layer - adapted from Crespo-Aguado et.al (2026), licensed under CC BY 4.0

3.3 Experimental evaluation: Resource utilisation and actuation latency

The technical measurements reported in this section were obtained in the companion architecture study (Crespo-Aguado et al., 2026); this paper does not claim them as primary results. Our contribution is the evaluation framework constructed around this evidence, which interprets these infrastructure-layer measurements as the quantitative anchors for the sustainability and operational indicators developed in Section 5. Crespo-Aguado et al. (2026) ran controlled experiments through four distinct execution phases: idle (baseline), processing of trigger events, actuation services running and post-actuation (teardown). The average amount of resources consumed for each execution phase is illustrated in Table 1.

Table 1 - Resource Consumption by Execution Phase (Source: Crespo-Aguado et al., 2026)

Execution Phase	CPU (mCPU)	Memory (MiB)	Interpretation
Baseline Idle	0.21	14.12	Always-on comparison baseline
Trigger Event Processing	0.55	14.23	Threshold detection, routing invocation
Actuation Service Active	21.74	15.68	Route-optimisation compute running
Post-Actuation Teardown	0.21	14.12	Service decommissioned; returns to idle

Data from Table 1 also shows how memory usage by the split-service architecture is dramatically lower than an always-on approach when the system is in idle state (which accounts for most of the time as it only becomes active when the container threshold is reached). At idle, memory consumption was only 14.12 MiB vs 29.89 MiB for a permanently activated application. Therefore, in its operational mode (idle), memory consumption has been reduced by 52.6%. The end-to-end actuation latency (i.e., the time elapsed between the activation signal generated by the sensor and the completion of the service instance creation) was 6.878 s, which is higher than expected but acceptable considering that the waste collection scheduling workflow cycle can last from a few hours to days.

These reported values serve as the quantitative anchors for the KPI framework developed in Section 5, specifically for indicators related to energy efficiency, operational cost, and infrastructure scalability, while all other indicators are populated by stakeholder input, baseline data, or planned measurement in later phases.

4. Methodology for framework development

The KPI/KVI evaluation framework proposed in this paper was developed using a four-phase iterative and mixed-methods approach for assessing multi-dimensional aspects of smart cities.

Phase 1: Systematic Literature Review - A systematic review of existing KPI-based smart city evaluation frameworks (ISO 37120, ISO 37122, CITYKEYS, ITU-T Y.4903), benchmark indicators for smart waste management, and performance indicators for edge computing was completed. This review also provided the operational definition of Key Values (KVs), Key Value Indicators (KVIs) and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). It clarified the differences between normative statements of what is desirable (KV), actual representations of the

stated values (KVI) and specific quantifiable measures (KPI).

Phase 2: Stakeholder Involvement - Stakeholders from the campus sustainability office of UPV, the environmental department of the Valencia City Council, Telefónica Innovación Digital (TID) and the COP-PILOT project management team were involved in structured interviews as part of Phase 2. These stakeholders were asked to rate the candidate indicators on two scales: how relevant these candidate indicators are to their decision-making processes and how feasible it will be to measure them with the data collected during the pilot. Candidate indicators that had ratings below the median value on both scales were removed or restructured.

Phase 3: Calibration Using Experimental Data - Quantitative targets for each KPI were calibrated using the following three types of calibration data: (a) the quantitative data collected in Crespo-Aguado et al. (2026), which is related to indicators of the infrastructure layer; (b) baseline data measured in the pre-pilot schedule of fixed time waste collection at UPV; (c) comparable data available in the literature where the data was not directly measurable.

Phase 4: Validation By Experts - The complete set of indicators compiled in Phases 1–3 was sent to a group of 5 independent experts in smart urban governance, IoT system design and environmental sustainability for validation. These experts reviewed the definitions of the indicators, the methods used to collect the data and the relationships between the different indicators. When all the experts agreed that the indicators were valid, revisions to the indicators were made, if necessary, until there was agreement that the indicators were valid (face validity).

5. Proposed evaluation framework for smart city applications

The framework divides evaluation into three areas: Sustainability (technical and environmental) and Societal Impact, as well as Business Value. In addition, all three areas are organised in terms of Key Values, which are the normative statements on desirable outcome, and therefore in terms of Key Value Indicators, which then have KPIs that can be used to measure them. Table 2, Table 3, and Table 4 contain the entire sets of indicators for each area of the framework.

5.1 Sustainability dimension

The sustainability dimension covers the environmental and resource efficiency aspects of enabling waste management via ICT at the edge of the network. A major structural insight of this work is that the split service deployment model - the edge based architectural design decision that leads to the 52.6% reduction in memory usage, is not only a form of engineering optimisation, but is also a key mechanism for achieving the sustainability objectives of the ICT infrastructure: i.e., by using minimal resources when it is idle (and since idle time dominates operational time), the system is able to avoid the constant consumption of energy associated with always-on cloud-based systems. The sustainability related KVI/KPI is listed in Table 1.

Table 1 - Sustainability dimension: Key value (KV), key value indicators (KVI) and key performance indicators (KPI)

KV	KVI	KPI Metric
Environmental resource stewardship	Dynamic collection maturity	Reduction in total vehicle-km driven vs fixed-schedule baseline
	Emissions-reduction potential	Litres of diesel saved per tonne of waste collected
		kg CO ₂ e avoided per annum on campus route
Infrastructure energy efficiency	Energy footprint of sensing	Mean mWh per fill-level transmission event
	Idle edge-node resource footprint	MiB consumed during no-threshold periods
	Elastic compute activation	ΔmCPU (actuation vs idle)
Scalable and transferable architecture	Deployment scalability	Deployment time for new Local Domain instance
	Multi-service concurrency under SLA constraints	Number of simultaneously active edge services without SLA degradation

5.2 Social dimension

The social dimension represents the quality of life in a city as experienced by residents. To make this connection from the social dimension to smart waste management, there needs to be a conceptual separation made between the indicators that are reported in the literature as "operational proxies" and those indicators which are truly experienced by citizens. The number of trips avoided because of an unnecessary trip (an operational proxy for

success) will have the impact of improving air quality, reducing noise pollution, and decreasing traffic congestion in residential neighbourhoods; it is these impacts that citizens experience and represent the real social benefit. The framework recognizes the importance of including both the operational proxy and the indicator for the citizen facing outcome and acknowledges that empirical evidence must be developed to understand the causal relationship between the two. The societal related KVI/KPI is listed in Table 3.

Table 2 - Societal Dimension: Key value (KV), key value indicators (KVI) and key performance indicators (KPI)

KV	KVI	KPI Metric
Urban quality of life	Collection efficiency vs disturbance	% of scheduled trips cancelled due to sub-threshold fill levels
	Service reliability at point of collection	Number of container overflow events per 100 containers per month
		Mean fill level (%) at point of collection
Civic trust and transparency	Perceived stakeholder satisfaction	Composite satisfaction score from staff, students and city council (1–5)
	Data governance assurance	% of data flows compliant with GDPR and zero-trust SIF policy
Public health and safety	Sanitation and nuisance incidents	Reported pest or sanitation incidents attributable to waste overflow
Digital inclusion	Accessibility of reporting and feedback	% of campus users able to report issues via LLM-powered natural language interface

5.3 Business value dimension

Business value dimension assesses how much the pilot contributes to three types of sustainable economics: (1) market; (2) financial; and (3) innovation ecosystems. The Business Value dimension is further divided into three sub-dimensions: (1) operational costs savings for a Campus Facilities Manager; (2) commercialization and take up of the platform by a Market; and (3) Innovation Maturity for EC TRL assessments. These are summarised in Table 3.

Table 3 - Business value dimension: Key value (KV), key value indicators (KVI) and key performance indicators (KPI)

KV	KVI	KPI Metric
Operational cost efficiency	Operational expenditure reduction	€ saved per annum on UPV campus collection contracts
	Infrastructure cost competitiveness	Total Cost of Ownership (edge deployment) / (cloud-only alternative)
	Fuel cost savings	€ fuel cost avoided per annum
Market development and uptake	External adoption of solution	Number of organisations adopting COP-PILOT framework post-pilot
	SME ecosystem engagement	Number of SMEs from COP-PILOT Open Calls using waste-management use case as reference
Innovation maturity	Technology readiness and validation	TRL at project conclusion (EC scale 1–9)
	KPI target achievement	% of KPI targets met across Phases 1–3

6. Discussion

6.1 Architecture as a Value-Creation Mechanism

A major argument in this paper is that the architectural choices made in the COP-PILOT platform are not simply engineering choices - they represent value-creation mechanisms, where the effects of the KPI/KVI framework can be traced.

For instance, the decision to deploy the services of the platform using a split-service approach does not simply

reduce the memory usage (a KPI in the sustainability dimension), because it reduces the idle-state energy draw, thus supporting the campus' objective of achieving carbon neutrality (a KV). In similar fashion, the zero-trust SIF architecture does not merely support a cybersecurity requirement but rather enables the achievement of the data-governance compliance KPI in the social dimension, which in turn underlies the civic trust KV.

The causal chain between the architectural choices and the governance relevant results is the most important difference between our framework and the existing evaluation methods. ISO 37120 and related standards, define the indicators without providing causal models; hence, the practitioner is unable to use them to reason about which architectural choices would produce which changes in the indicators. Our framework provides this reasoning explicitly, so the practitioner is able to make informed procurement and design decisions.

6.2 Positioning relative to existing frameworks

Our framework is positioned in a unique position in the evaluation space. City-level frameworks (ISO 37120, CITYKEYS) evaluate at a scale and pace that is too large to measure the dynamic behaviour of a single deployment of an IoT Edge solution. Service-level frameworks (TM Forum TMF633) evaluate at a scale that is too small to measure governance relevant results. Our framework measures at a middle ground, transforming infrastructure metrics (memory footprint, actuation latency) to service level outcomes (unneeded trips removed, overflow events reduced) to then transform those service outcomes to governance relevant values (sustainability, civic trust, economic efficiency).

6.3 Transferability and limitations

Our framework was created for a specific use case, namely a university campus in southern Europe with available NB-IoT network coverage, active Horizon Europe project infrastructure and a commitment to sustainability. Transferability to other use cases, such as lower resource municipal districts, industrial parks with differing waste typology, historic city centres with limited sensor placement, etc., will likely require significant adaptation. Specifically, the fill-level threshold values we defined for UPV's container types may not be applicable elsewhere; the stakeholder satisfaction survey will need to be adapted for non-academic communities; the TRL based innovation maturity indicators assume European Commission reporting requirements that are not universal. Another limitation relates to the time dimension; our framework is evaluated on the basis of the baseline data from Phase 1, and the empirical values from Phases 2 and 3 will undoubtedly require recalibrating the indicators. This is not a flaw in the methodology, but rather a design element of our iterative method; the framework is a living tool, not a static score card.

7. Conclusion

We have provided a multi-dimensional KPI/KVI framework to evaluate the effectiveness of an edge-enabled smart waste management system in the COP-PILOT smart-city pilot at the University of Politecnica de Valencia. Our framework comprises twenty KVIs, operationalised through twenty-two KPIs, spanning the sustainability, social-impact and business-value dimensions. We have also demonstrated how the empirical data collected from our actual deployment of ETSI NGSI-LD / OpenSlice / OpenZiti in an actual environment is correlated with systematic stakeholder input.

We have shown how two infrastructure-layer measurements, i.e. a 52.6% reduction in idle memory under the split-service model and a 6.878-second end-to-end actuation latency can be mapped, through the framework's KVI logic, to sustainability, operational and civic-welfare values that traditional technical benchmarking leaves unmeasured. The framework specifies these linkages; confirming them empirically requires the longitudinal, multi-phase data discussed below. By making explicit the hypothesised causal pathways linking architectural decisions to governance-relevant outcomes, our framework allows designers and evaluators to reason about trade-offs in terms that are meaningful to all stakeholders, including city managers, environmental regulators, and citizens. Establishing these pathways empirically, beyond the infrastructure-layer evidence reported here, is the central task of the framework's later evaluation phases.

The next steps of the research will be directed toward extending the framework in three main areas. Firstly, we will perform a multi-domain replication in the Port of Valencia to validate the comparative aspects of the framework. Secondly, we will connect the LLM/RAG conversational observability layer, currently being designed as part of COP-PILOT Phase 3, to the civic trust KVI, to test if a natural language interface to waste data increases citizen engagement and self-reported satisfaction. Thirdly, we will perform a comparative analysis of the framework in relation to the smart waste management pilots of the cities belonging to COP-PILOT clusters 3 (Greece) and 4 (Germany/Spain), to verify the transferability of the framework across different urban typologies and governance regimes.

Smart waste management, considered from the perspective of what we have developed here, is not just a logistics

problem, but an institutional one: it requires evaluation tools that can speak to both engineers, city planners and democratic publics. The KPI/KVI framework that we have developed in this paper is offered as a contribution to that multi-register conversation.

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Use of AI

During the preparation of this work, the author(s) used to Perplexity.ai to identify and locate relevant literature and sources, and Grammarly to proofread the document. After using this tool/service, the author(s) reviewed, edited, made the content their own and validated the outcome as needed, and take(s) full responsibility for the content of the publication

Declarations

Conflict Of Interest (COI)

There is no conflict of interest.

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None

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